

Potential supplements to cell theory

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For reasons that remain unclear, despite roughly 4 billion years of cellular evolution, cell theory has only three well-accepted postulates¹. I previously proposed the gasocrine hypothesis, which states that all cells require gasocrine signaling². However, this can be expanded into a broader postulate that extends beyond the signaling aspects of gases to other environmental factors as well. I propose that "**All cells are limited by their environment**". One simple falsification experiment would be to find a cell in an extreme temperature (e.g., approx. 5000°C as on the Sun). Thus, the statement is another potential supplement to the cell theory.

REFERENCES

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